

THE INFLUENCE OF PARENTING STYLES AND SELF-COMPASSION ON THE ACADEMIC PROCRASTINATION AMONG MATHEMATICS EDUCATION STUDENTS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 8

Pages: 1336-1357

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2816

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14568941

Manuscript Accepted: 11-22-2024

The Influence of Parenting Styles and Self-Compassion on the Academic Procrastination among Mathematics Education Students

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Abstract

The purpose of the study was to determine the influence of parenting styles and self-compassion on academic procrastination among mathematics education students in a local college in Davao del Norte. The study is quantitative research that utilizes a descriptive-correlational approach. A sample of 152 randomly selected mathematics education students who were identified using stratified random sampling answered the surveys on the three variables. This study used the following statistical tools to obtain the results: mean, Pearson r , and regression. Results showed that the level of parenting styles and self-compassion were high, while the level of academic procrastination was moderate. Results also revealed that there is a significant relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination. Likewise, there is also a significant relationship between self-compassion and academic procrastination. Moreover, results show that domains of parenting styles such as authoritarian parenting and permissive parenting can significantly influence academic procrastination. Finally, it was revealed that domains of self-compassion, such as self-kindness, isolation, and over-identification, can significantly predict the academic procrastination of the respondents. Results imply that the variables influence the academic procrastination of mathematics education students.

Keywords: *parenting styles, self-compassion, academic procrastination, mathematics education students, Philippines*

Introduction

Procrastination is a pervasive issue affecting individuals across various aspects of life, leading to many negative outcomes. Research has consistently demonstrated that procrastination is a significant factor influencing life satisfaction, particularly among the elderly. For instance, a study among elderly found that procrastination directly contributes to lower life satisfaction, highlighting how the tendency to delay important tasks can undermine personal well-being (Pirzadeh-Nouri et al., 2021). This impact extends beyond just life satisfaction, as procrastination is also closely linked to work engagement and job performance. Workers who procrastinate tend to disengage from their tasks, often spending time on non-work-related activities during work hours. This disengagement not only decreases the quality of work but also reduces overall productivity, further reinforcing the negative effects of procrastination on professional life (Metin et al., 2018). These negative outcomes are not limited to personal and professional spheres; they also extend to financial stability. Procrastination often leads to financial problems, not due to poor planning but because of a failure to execute planned actions. This lack of follow-through can result in delayed bill payments and insufficient savings, which compound financial stress (Gamst-Klaussen et al., 2019). Moreover, the fallouts of procrastination are evident in health-related outcomes as well, a study found that chronic procrastination is associated with various mental health issues, including symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. It also contributes to unhealthy lifestyle behaviors, such as poor sleep quality and physical inactivity, which further exacerbate health problems (Johansson et al., 2023).

Academic procrastination, a specific subset of this issue, is a global problem that significantly impacts students' academic performance and overall well-being. Approximately 80% of university students in the Amhara Region, Ethiopia, admit to regularly procrastinating on academic tasks, which negatively affects their grades and learning outcomes, resulting in academic failure (Fentaw et al., 2022). Meanwhile, a study among university students in Moscow, Samara, and Nizhny Novgorod shows that procrastinating students often experience higher levels of stress. They are more likely to experience frustration and dissatisfaction (Kuflyak, 2022). Even more concerning, it was found that academic procrastination is a strong predictor of dropout rates decreasing graduation rates, as students who consistently delay their studies are more likely to disengage and eventually leave school; this happened in an economics school of a research university in the Netherlands (Arnold, 2023). An interesting longitudinal study in Beijing, China, found that over time, as the age of their respondents increases, their level of self-esteem declines, and as their self-esteem decreases, their level of academic procrastination increases (Yang et al., 2021).

In the Philippines, academic procrastination is a significant issue, adversely affecting students at various educational levels. For instance, a study among Office Administration students in NCR (National Capital Region) shows that academic procrastination negatively correlates with academic performance; high academic procrastination results in low school performance (Nartea et al., 2020). The same problem can be seen from the study among Filipino secondary students; it was shown that there is a negative significant relationship between academic procrastination and academic achievement, implying that the more learners procrastinate, the lower their academic grades (Caratiquit & Caratiquit, 2023). Not only does academic procrastination negatively affect students academically, but it also affects their well-being. 5 out of 10 or 50% of the participants in a qualitative study said that academic procrastination negatively affects their physical and mental health; this is because of the exhaustion and panic brought by the bulk of workloads as well as being overloaded with backlogs (Lao et al., 2023). Many factors cause students to procrastinate, either internal or external, or both. Some of these are digital distractions, outdoor activities, beating the deadline, fear of failure, lack of motivation or interest, easy

distraction, and lack of skills to do the activities (Domingo, 2023). All previous studies mentioned show that procrastination is a common problem with big effects on many areas of life, including work, mental health, and overall happiness. Even though it is so widespread, we still do not fully understand why people procrastinate or how it affects them in the long run. More research is needed to figure out how to tackle this issue because it is holding back many people's personal and professional growth.

By investigating how parenting styles and self-compassion influence academic procrastination, this study provides valuable insights with several benefits. Understanding these relationships can lead to improved teaching strategies, enhanced student mental health, and more effective parental support. This, in turn, helps reduce academic gaps and contributes to the overall success and well-being of students, particularly in math education students, and broader society. Additionally, the issue of academic procrastination needs urgent attention, and understanding its causes is essential. Academic procrastination is often viewed as an independent variable that negatively affects students' performance. To effectively address this problem, we must first understand what causes procrastination. We need to delve deeply into the factors that lead to procrastination and examine how these factors contribute to its occurrence and severity. By addressing these root causes, we can develop more effective strategies to mitigate procrastination and improve student outcomes.

As per reviews on related literature, several studies regarding the three variables were published, such as the study conducted by Amani and Arbabi (2020), "The Mediating Role of Academic Self-Regulation in the Relationship between Parenting Dimensions and Academic Procrastination." This study showed a relationship between the two variables, parenting styles and academic procrastination. There was another study, too, by Sapançi (2021) showing how self-compassion could impact academic procrastination, "The Mediating Role of Self-Compassion in the Relationship between Perfectionism and Academic Procrastination in Pre-service Teachers". Lastly, a study conducted by Hayat et al. (2020), "Prevalence of Academic Procrastination Among Medical Students and its Relationship with Their Academic Achievement," this study showed how procrastination can affect the academic achievement of medical students in a particular university. Although we could see relationships among these three variables through the studies presented, there was no regression study yet about academic procrastination and the two independent variables. Additionally, this research has mathematics major education students as respondents, and no study like this has been conducted on them yet. To address both the gap and the necessity of conducting a study about academic procrastination among mathematics education students, the researcher recognized the need to conduct a study that determines the influence of parenting styles and self-compassion on academic procrastination among the said respondents.

Moreover, this study will contribute valuable insights not only within our institution but also to a broader academic and professional community. The findings will be disseminated through various research conferences and shared with relevant organizations to foster knowledge exchange and promote the practical application of the study's outcomes. As a result, the significance and implications of this research will extend to a wider audience, helping to address the identified issues and facilitate the implementation of the proposed recommendations.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to examine the mediating effect of self-compassion on the relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination. Specifically, this study answered the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of parenting styles in terms of:
 - 1.1. authoritative;
 - 1.2. authoritarian; and
 - 1.3. permissive
2. To determine the level of self-compassion in terms of:
 - 2.1. self-kindness;
 - 2.2. self-judgment;
 - 2.3. common humanity;
 - 2.4. isolation;
 - 2.5. mindfulness; and
 - 2.6. over-identification
3. To determine the level of academic procrastination in terms of:
 - 3.1. poor time management;
 - 3.2. work disconnection, and
 - 3.3. core procrastination
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. parenting styles and academic procrastination, and
 - 4.2. self-compassion and academic procrastination
5. To determine which domain/s of parenting styles and self-compassion significantly affect academic procrastination among mathematics education students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a quantitative research design with a descriptive-correlational method. The main objectives were to assess the influence of parenting styles and self-compassion on academic procrastination among mathematics education students. This approach involved gathering and analyzing numerical data to examine and quantify different variables, aiming to draw significant conclusions. A quantitative research design is a structured framework that guides the process of collecting and analyzing numerical data to answer research questions or test hypotheses. It includes the selection of a suitable method, such as experimental, correlational, or descriptive design, to systematically measure variables. The design specifies the procedures for sampling, data collection, and the use of statistical tools for analysis (Creswell, 2014).

In the context of this study, quantitative research was employed because it allows for the precise measurement and statistical analysis of variables. This approach enables the identification of patterns, correlations, and potential causal relationships between parenting styles, self-compassion, and academic procrastination. By using standardized instruments and large sample sizes, quantitative research ensures the reliability and generalizability of the findings. Additionally, it facilitates the objective evaluation of hypotheses, contributing to a clearer understanding of the factors influencing academic procrastination among the specific population.

Specifically, this study employed a quantitative descriptive correlational design to describe the relationship variables. A descriptive correlational design is a research method used to observe and measure the relationship between two or more variables without manipulating them. It aims to describe the strength and direction of associations between variables while identifying patterns and trends in the data. This design does not attempt to establish cause-and-effect relationships but provides valuable insight into how variables might be connected. Researchers use this method to quantify the degree of association, typically through statistical measures like correlation coefficients. Descriptive correlational studies are useful in exploring relationships in natural settings, helping to form hypotheses for future research while maintaining the integrity of existing conditions (Seeram, 2019).

In this study, a descriptive correlational design was used to measure and describe the relationships between parenting style, self-compassion, and academic procrastination. By observing and analyzing the degree of association between these variables without manipulating them, the study could reveal patterns and trends, such as whether certain parenting styles are linked to higher or lower levels of procrastination or how self-compassion influences students' academic behaviors. This approach would not establish causation but would provide insights into the strength and direction of the relationships between these factors.

Respondents

The respondents of this study involved mathematics education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology located in the Municipality of Kapalong, Province of Davao del Norte. Particularly, these included first-year, second-year, third-year, and fourth-year students from BSEd-Mathematics. It was with the intent to conduct the research focusing on one program with a particular major – homogeneity of the sample, the mathematics education students. This can reduce noise in the data and clearly see patterns of behaviors, particularly academic procrastination, given that mathematics education students are likely to share similar backgrounds, experiences, and challenges related to their academic pursuits.

Further, Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents of this study. In collecting the sample, the researcher initially acquired the population data by drafting an official request letter to the college registrar, seeking permission to access the

Respondent pool. Subsequently, upon obtaining the data, the researcher forwarded it to their statistician for computing the study's sample.

To ensure an accurate distribution of samples, stratified random sampling was used, utilizing proportional allocation through Slovin's formula with a margin of error of 0.05. From within each stratum, uniform random sampling was used to select a per-stratum sample. All per-stratum samples are combined to derive the stratified random sample (Nguyen et al., 2020). In this case, the strata are the four year-levels of mathematics education students in Kapalong College Agriculture Sciences and Technology.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1st Year	119	74	30.13%
2nd Year	50	31	12.66%
3rd Year	43	27	10.89%
4th Year	33	20	8.36%
Total	245	152	62.04%

Table 1 presents the distribution of respondents across different year levels. The total population under study comprises 245 students, with a sample size of 152 respondents, accounting for 62.04% of the total population.

The breakdown of the respondents by year level is as follows: The largest group of respondents comes from the 1st Year, with 74 respondents out of a population of 119, representing 30.13% of the total population. The 2nd Year students contribute 31 respondents

from a population of 50, making up 12.66% of the total population. The 3rd Year group has 27 respondents out of 43 students, which is 10.89% of the population. Finally, the 4th-year students represent the smallest group, with 20 respondents from a population of 33, making up 8.36% of the total population.

Instrument

The study employed a five-point Likert scale to assess respondents' observation levels for the three variables. The five-point Likert scale was adopted and modified from the study of Adelson and McCoach (2010) such that this study modified it to the Frequency Likert scale having the following interpretation of values: 5 – Always, 4 – Oftentimes, 3 – Sometimes, 2 – Seldom, and 1 – Never. The researcher found it relevant to use the scale in this study since 5-point Likert scales are globally considered reliable scales in measuring perceptions, behavior, and attitudes (Sullivan & Artino, 2013).

Since this study aimed to measure parenting styles, self-compassion, and academic procrastination, which are aligned with behavior and attitude, it is just ideal to use a 5-point Likert scale. A Likert scale is a psychometric scale commonly used in questionnaires to measure people's attitudes, opinions, or perceptions. It allows respondents to specify their level of agreement or disagreement on a symmetric agree-disagree scale for a series of statements. Typically, the scale ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, with several intermediate options. This method is widely used in surveys because it provides a quantitative measure of subjective attributes (Likert, 1932).

The study adopted three questionnaires from web sources to measure the variables. The instrument used to measure parenting styles was the Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) by Buri (1991). The parenting styles have three subdimensions: authoritarian style with five items, authoritative style with five items, and permissive style with five items. A testing session over 2 weeks was conducted to test the reliability of this questionnaire, and it yielded .95, meeting the excellent reliability level of Cronbach's alpha when it was contextualized to the students' mother and .93, meeting also the excellent reliability level, when contextualized to student's father. This concludes that the PAQ is reliable in assessing the permissiveness, authoritarianism, and authoritativeness of students' parents. In describing the parenting styles, the five-point Likert-type scale was used.

As for self-compassion, the Self-Compassion Scale (SCS) by Neff (2003) was the questionnaire that was used for the second independent variable, self-compassion. It has six components: self-kindness, self-judgment, common humanity, isolation, mindfulness, and over-identified – all having 5 items each. A good test-retest reliability was obtained when the responses to the Self-Compassion Scale were compared across Time 1 and Time 2. The internal consistency for the 26-item questionnaire was .92, passing the excellent reliability level of Cronbach's alpha. The five-point Likert-type scale was also used in describing students' self-compassion.

Lastly, the questionnaire Multidimensional Academic Procrastination Scale (MAPS-15) by Brignardello and Panlagua (2023) was utilized. Academic procrastination has three components, namely core procrastination consisting of five items, poor time management with five items, and work disconnection with five items, too. The reliability of each item of MAPS-15 met the criterion, which is $\geq .25$. According to the Condensed Test Report, 0.25 is one recommended cut-off for useful questions. In describing academic procrastination, the five-point Likert-type scale was used.

Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher observed the following steps.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher sought permission from the College President of KCAST through a letter to allow the researcher to conduct the study among mathematics education students. After getting the approval of the College President, the researcher sent letters to the College Registrar and the Vice-President for Academic Affairs. Then, the researcher notified the program coordinator of the Bachelor of Secondary Education—Mathematics as well as the panel members for them to be fully aware of the conduct of the study.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. After the approval of the College President, the researcher then sought assistance from the program coordinator of Bachelor of Secondary Education—Mathematics as well as the mayors from each section for the dissemination of questionnaires. The collection of data was to be done online through Google Forms and face-to-face with paper and pencil, according to which way students found it convenient to answer the questionnaires.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were used in the computation of data.

Mean. In this study, this was used to determine the level of parenting styles, academic procrastination, and self-compassion.

Pearson r. In this study, this was used to test the relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination, parenting styles and self-compassion, and self-compassion and academic procrastination.

Regression. In this study, this statistical tool was used to identify the specific area or domain within parenting styles and self-compassion that has a significant impact on the academic procrastination of students.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of this study were students from the Bachelor of Secondary Education—Mathematics at Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology. In this case, the researcher made sure that their safety, rights, and trust in the researcher and the purpose of the study would be given rightful action and justice.

Maintaining high ethical standards is essential when conducting research involving human participants. The primary aim of this quantitative study was to ensure ethical soundness and protect the well-being of the participants. The researcher evaluated how the study adhered to the core ethical principles outlined by Denzin and Lincoln (2011), which include informed consent, minimizing risk of harm, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality, and addressing potential conflicts of interest.

Informed consent is the primary core principle of ethical considerations. Researchers must thoroughly disclose the study's requirements, the intended use of the data, and any potential consequences to the participants. Participants must provide their explicit, active, and written consent to take part in the study. They should also be informed of their right to access their information and their ability to withdraw consent at any time. An agreement between the researcher and the participants is a key component of obtaining informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

To ensure informed consent, the researcher included a question in the Google survey forms asking participants if they were willing to participate in the study, considering the potential risks involved. Participants had the option to decline if they were unsure about their consent. The study encouraged participants to make informed decisions and engage voluntarily. The researcher also ensured that all participants were genuinely interested in the project and eager to participate. During data collection, it was important to adhere to the responses based on the provided questionnaires.

The second core principle of ethical considerations is managing the risk of harm, maintaining confidentiality, and ensuring anonymity. This involves safeguarding participants so that their identities cannot be connected to their data by anyone, including the researcher, and preventing the disclosure of their identity to anyone other than those authorized (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

Notably, the researcher ensured the participants' safety and protection of their identity and personal information, treating them as valued contributors to the study. To ensure a secure data collection process, the researcher removed any identifying details from the data. The collected data did not include information that could identify respondents, such as names or addresses, with such identifying details stored separately in protected files.

Conflicts of Interest are the third core aspect of ethical considerations. It acknowledges that existing relationships or prior activities of the researcher could lead to conflicts of interest, which must be disclosed transparently in an ethics approval application so the committee can offer guidance on managing them. Conflicts arise when personal interests or commitments are prioritized over research responsibilities or when there is a perception of such prioritization. These conflicts can be actual, hypothetical, or perceived and may involve monetary or non-monetary incentives. Such conflicts may compromise a researcher's objectivity and judgment or be perceived as doing so, potentially undermining the credibility of the research findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

In this context, there were no external factors influencing the research outcomes since the respondents were students and the researcher had no conflicts of interest. Conflicts of interest typically arise when a researcher has the power to coerce participants into taking part through threats, such as blackmail, the withholding of benefits, or other forms of punishment. For example, conflicts might occur if teachers threatened to fail students who did not complete the survey or if principals threatened to terminate teachers who did not participate.

Results and Discussion

Level of Parenting Style in Terms of Authoritative Parenting

The level of parenting styles observed by mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of authoritative parenting. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 2. *Level of Parenting Style in Terms of Authoritative Parenting Style*

	<i>Authoritative</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Directing the activities and decisions of the children in the family through reasoning and discipline	4.07	High
2.	Encouraging verbal give-and-take whenever I am feeling that family rules and restrictions are unreasonable	4.07	High
3.	Giving me direction and guidance in rational and objective ways	4.14	High
4.	Taking my opinions into consideration when making family decisions but do not decide on something simply because I want it	4.06	High
5.	Giving me clear direction for my behaviors and activities, they are also understanding when I disagree with them	4.24	High
	Overall	4.11	High

Presented in Table 2 is the level of parenting styles in terms of authoritative parenting style. The data revealed that parenting styles, in terms of authoritative parenting, had an overall mean score of 4.11, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the students oftentimes observed the level of parenting style in terms of authoritative parenting style.

The highest mean is 4.24, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observe the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 5 - Giving me clear direction for my behaviors and activities; they are also understanding when I disagree with them.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 4.06, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observe the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 4 – Taking my opinions into consideration when making a family.

Level of Parenting Styles in Terms of Authoritarian Parenting

The level of parenting styles observed by mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of authoritarian parenting. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of parenting styles in terms of authoritarian parenting style. The data revealed that parenting styles, in terms of authoritarian parenting, had an overall mean score of 3.57 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that mathematics education students oftentimes observe the level of parenting style in terms of authoritarian parenting style.

The highest mean score is 3.84, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 1 - Expecting me to do things they tell me to do immediately without asking any questions.

In contrast, the lowest mean score is 3.39, which is described as moderate. This means that the respondents sometimes observed the item. This corresponds to the statement no. 3 - Letting me know what behavior they are expecting of me, and if I do not meet those expectations, they punish me.

Table 3. *Level of Parenting Style in Terms of Authoritarian Parenting Style*

	<i>Authoritarian</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Expecting me to do things they tell me to do immediately without asking any questions		3.84	High
2. Not allowing me to question any decision they make		3.52	High
3. Letting me know what behavior they are expecting of me, and if I do not meet those expectations, they punish me		3.39	Moderate
4. Feeling that wise parents must teach their children early just who the boss in the family		3.52	High
5. Getting very upset if I try to disagree with them		3.56	High
	Overall	3.57	High

Level of Parenting Style in Terms of Permissive Parenting

The level of parenting styles observed by mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator permissive parenting. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of parenting styles in terms of permissive parenting style. The data revealed that parenting styles in terms of permissive parenting style, had an overall mean score of 3.68, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that mathematics education students oftentimes observe the parenting styles in terms of permissive parenting.

The highest mean score is 3.91 which means high. This means that the respondents of the study oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 5 – Not allowing me to form my point of view on family matters and generally allowing me to decide for myself what I am going to do.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.41, which means moderate. This means that the respondents sometimes observed the item. This corresponds to statement no. 4 – Not viewing themselves as responsible for directing and guiding my behavior.

Table 4. *Level of Parenting Style in Terms of Permissive Parenting Style*

	<i>Permissive</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Doing what the children in the family want when making family decisions		3.74	High
2. Allowing me to decide most things for myself without a lot of direction from them		3.74	High
3. Not directing the behaviors, activities, and desires of the children in the family		3.59	High
4. Not viewing themselves as responsible for directing and guiding my behavior		3.41	Moderate
5. Not allowing me to form my own point of view on family matters and generally allowing me to decide for myself what I am going to do		3.91	High
	Overall	3.68	High

Summary of the Level of Parenting Styles

Table 5 provides an overview of the overall parenting styles observed by mathematics education students – authoritative parenting style, authoritarian parenting style, and permissive parenting style.

The data revealed that the overall mean of parenting style, as reported by mathematics education students, had a total mean score of 3.79, with the descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This suggests that the level of parenting style of mathematics education students' parents was oftentimes observed.

Further, the highest mean score among the indicators is 4.11, which belongs to the indicator, authoritative parenting style, with the descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of parenting style of mathematics education students' parents in terms of authoritative parenting is oftentimes observed.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the indicators is 3.57, which belongs to the indicator authoritarian parenting style, with the descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of parenting of mathematics education students' parents in terms of authoritarian parenting is oftentimes observed.

Lastly, the permissive parenting style garnered a mean score of 3.68 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of parenting style of Mathematics education students' parents, with a focus on permissive parenting, were oftentimes observed.

Table 5. Summary on the Level of Parenting Styles

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Authoritative	4.11	High
Authoritarian	3.57	High
Permissive	3.68	High
Overall	3.79	High

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Self-Kindness

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of self-kindness. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 is the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students in terms of self-kindness. The data revealed that self-compassion, in terms of self-kindness, had an overall mean score of 4.16 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of self-kindness, was oftentimes manifested by the students.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 4.29 with a descriptive equivalent of very high. This means that the respondents always manifested the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 5 - Trying to be loving towards myself when I am feeling emotional pain.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.91 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 4 - Being tolerant of my own flaws and inadequacies.

Table 6. Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Self-Kindness

<i>Self-Kindness</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to be understanding and patient towards those aspects of my personality I do not like	4.22	High
2.	Being kind to myself when I am experiencing suffering	4.13	High
3.	Giving myself the caring and tenderness I need when I am going through a very hard time	4.24	High
4.	Being tolerant of my own flaws and inadequacies.	3.91	High
5.	Trying to be loving towards myself when I am feeling emotional pain.	4.29	Very High
Overall		4.16	High

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Self-Judgement

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of self-judgment. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 7. Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Self-Judgment

<i>Self-Judgment</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Getting down on myself when I see aspects of myself that I do not like	3.86	High
Being tough on myself when times are really difficult	3.91	High
Becoming a bit cold-hearted towards myself when I am experiencing suffering	3.86	High
Disapproving and judgmental about my own flaws and inadequacies	3.85	High
Being intolerant and impatient towards those aspects of my personality that I do not like	3.80	High
Overall	3.86	High

Table 7 presents the levels of self-compassion among mathematics education students in terms of self-judgment. The data revealed that self-compassion, in terms of self-judgment, had an overall mean score of 3.86 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of self-judgment, was oftentimes manifested by the students.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.91, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 2 - Being tough on myself when times are really difficult.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.80, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 5 – Being intolerant and impatient towards those aspects of my personality that I do not like.

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Common Humanity

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator common humanity. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 8 presents the levels of self-compassion among mathematics education students concerning common humanity. The data revealed that self-compassion in terms of common humanity had an overall mean score of 4.14 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of common humanity, was oftentimes manifested by the respondents.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 4.26, with a descriptive equivalent categorized as very high. This means that the respondents always manifested the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 5 - “Feeling a sense of connection with others when I hear about their challenges.”

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.96, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 1 – Trying to remind myself that feelings of inadequacy are shared by most people whenever I feel inadequate.

Table 8. *Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Common Humanity*

	<i>Common Humanity</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to remind myself that feelings of inadequacy are shared by most people whenever I feel inadequate	3.96	High
2.	Trying to see my failings as part of the human condition	4.15	High
3.	Reminding myself that there are lots of other people in the world feeling like I am whenever I am down and out	4.17	High
4.	Seeing difficulties as part of life that everyone goes through whenever things are going badly for me	4.18	High
5.	Feeling a sense of connection with others when I hear about their challenges	4.26	Very High
	Overall	4.14	High

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Isolation

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator isolation. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 9 presents the levels of self-compassion among mathematics education students concerning isolation. The data revealed that self-compassion, as observed in terms of isolation, had an overall mean score of 3.80 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of isolation, was oftentimes manifested by the students.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.99, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 1 – Feeling alone in my failure when I fail at something important to me.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.72, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 5 – Believing that others would not be able to relate to my problems.

Table 9. *Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Isolation*

	<i>Isolation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Feeling alone in my failure when I fail at something important to me	3.99	High
2.	Feeling more separate and cut off from the rest of the world when I think about my inadequacies	3.81	High
3.	Feeling that other people are most probably happier than I am whenever I am feeling down	3.75	High
4.	Feeling that other people are having an easier time than me whenever I am really struggling	3.74	High
5.	Believing that others will not be able to relate to my problems	3.72	High
	Overall	3.80	High

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Mindfulness

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator mindfulness. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 10 presents the levels of self-compassion among mathematics education students concerning mindfulness. The data revealed that self-compassion, as observed by mathematics education students in terms of mindfulness, had an overall mean score of 4.05 with a descriptive eq of high. This suggests that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of mindfulness, was oftentimes manifested by the students.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 4.14, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 1 – Trying to keep my emotions in balance when something upsets me.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.99 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 5 – Being aware of my emotions without being overly reactive or overwhelmed by them.

Table 10. *Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Mindfulness*

	<i>Mindfulness</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Trying to keep my emotions in balance when something upsets me	4.14	High
2.	Trying to approach my feelings with curiosity and openness when I am feeling down	4.06	High
3.	Trying to take a balanced view of the situation when something painful happens	4.05	High
4.	Trying to keep things in perspective when I fail at something	4.01	High
5.	Being aware of my emotions without being overly reactive or overwhelmed by them	3.99	High
	Overall	4.05	High

Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Over-Identification

The level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of over-identification. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 11 presents the levels of self-compassion among mathematics education students concerning over-identification. The data revealed that self-compassion, as observed by mathematics education students in terms of over-identification, had an overall mean score of 3.77 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of over-identification, was oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.88, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 1 - Getting carried away with my feelings when something upsets me.

In contrast, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.69, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes manifested the item. This corresponds to statement no. 5 - Becoming entangled in my problems, unable to step back and see the bigger picture.

Table 11. *Level of Self-Compassion in Terms of Over-Identification*

	<i>Over-Identification</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Getting carried away with my feelings when something upsets me	3.88	High
2.	Obsessing and fixating on everything wrong when I am feeling down	3.82	High
3.	Blowing the incident out of proportion when something painful happens	3.76	High
4.	Becoming consumed by feelings of inadequacy when I fail at something important	3.72	High
5.	Becoming entangled in my problems, unable to step back and see the bigger picture	3.69	High
	Overall	3.77	High

Summary of the Level of Self-Compassion

Table 12 provides an overview of the overall self-compassion of mathematics education students and its indicators: self-kindness, self-judgment, common humanity, isolation, mindfulness, and over-identification.

The data revealed that the overall mean of self-compassion, as reported by mathematics education students, had a total mean score of 3.96, with a descriptive equivalent categorized as high. This suggests that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students was oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean score among the indicators is 4.16, which belongs to the indicator of self-kindness. This, therefore, indicates a descriptive equivalence of high. This means that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students in terms of self-kindness is oftentimes manifested.

Furthermore, the lowest mean score among the indicators is 3.77 which belongs to the indicator over-identification. This, therefore, indicates a descriptive equivalence of high. This means that the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students in terms of over-identification is oftentimes manifested.

Table 12. *Summary on the Level of Self-Compassion*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Self-Kindness	4.16	High
Self-Judgment	3.86	High
Common Humanity	4.14	High
Isolation	3.80	High
Mindfulness	4.05	High
Over-Identification	3.77	High
Overall	3.77	High

In addition, it is worth noting that the common humanity indicator, which is the second highest, obtained a score of 4.14, signifying a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, specifically in terms of common humanity, was oftentimes manifested.

Also, the indicator mindfulness was the third highest, obtaining a mean score of 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, specifically in terms of mindfulness, was oftentimes manifested.

Moreover, the self-judgment indicator yielded a mean score of 3.86, signifying a high level based on the description. This suggests that the self-compassion of mathematics education students, particularly in terms of self-judgment, was oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, the indicator isolation garnered a mean score of 3.80 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students, with a focus on isolation, was oftentimes manifested.

Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Poor Time-Management

The level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of poor time management. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 13. *Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Poor Time-management*

<i>Poor Time-Management</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Being behind with my work	3.50	High
2.	Not sticking to a study routine	3.38	Moderate
3.	Not keeping on top of my studies	3.28	Moderate
4.	Not managing to study everything I set out to study for a session	3.39	Moderate
5.	Packing my schedule so full that I do not have time if an emergency arises	3.22	Moderate
Overall		3.35	Moderate

Table 13 presents the levels of academic procrastination among mathematics education students in terms of poor time management. The data revealed that Academic procrastination, in terms of poor time management, had an overall mean score of 3.35, signifying a moderate level based on the description. This suggests that the level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students, particularly in terms of poor time management, was sometimes observed.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.50 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to the statement no. 1 – Being behind with my work.”

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.22, also signifying a moderate level based on the description. This means that the respondents sometimes observed the item. This corresponds to statement no. 5 - Packing my schedule so full that I do not have time if an emergency arises.

Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Work Disconnection

The level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of work disconnection. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 14 presents the levels of academic procrastination among mathematics education students in terms of work disconnection. The data revealed that academic procrastination, in terms of work disconnection, had an overall mean score of 3.33, with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that the level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students, particularly in terms of work disconnection, was sometimes observed.

Table 14. *Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Work Disconnection*

<i>Work Disconnection</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Working in a non-systematic, disorganized way	3.20	Moderate
2.	Interrupting my work to go out, have a coffee, walk around, chat with someone etc.	3.26	Moderate
3.	Thinking that I will be able to do more things in a day than I can get done	3.51	High
4.	Wasting time doing other things when I am studying and preparing for exams	3.38	Moderate
5.	Wasting a lot of time on irrelevant information before I get down to the main ideas of a subject	3.32	Moderate
Overall		3.33	Moderate

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.51 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to the statement no. 3 – Thinking that I will be able to do more things in a day than I can actually get done.

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.20, with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This means that the respondents sometimes observed the item. This corresponds to the statement – Working in a non-systematic or disorganized way.

Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Core Procrastination

The level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator core procrastination. The responses of the respondents on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 15. *Level of Academic Procrastination in Terms of Core Procrastination*

<i>Core Procrastination</i>		<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1.	Working on my task on and off when I feel like it	3.72	High
2.	Wanting to have a real incentive to study or work on my task	3.66	High
3.	Finding it difficult to make a decision to start studying or doing my task	3.54	High
4.	Postponing studying or doing my task because I think I still have a lot of time left to do it	3.55	High
5.	Engaging in activities that may be more appealing instead of studying right away	3.46	High
Overall		3.58	High

Table 15 presents the levels of academic procrastination among mathematics education students concerning core procrastination. The data revealed that academic procrastination, in terms of core procrastination, had an overall mean score of 3.58 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This suggests that the level of academic procrastination among mathematics education students, particularly in terms of core procrastination, was oftentimes observed.

The highest mean score among the survey items is 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 1 – Working on my task on and off when I feel like it.

Further, the lowest mean score among the survey items is 3.46, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the respondents oftentimes observed the item. This level corresponds to statement no. 5 – Engaging in activities that may be more appealing instead of studying right away.

Summary of the Level of Academic Procrastination

Table 16 provides an overview of the overall academic procrastination of mathematics education students and its indicators: work disconnection, poor time management, and core procrastination.

Table 16. *Summary on the Level of Academic Procrastination*

<i>Indicators</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Poor Time Management	3.35	Moderate
Work Disconnection	3.33	Moderate
Core Procrastination	3.58	High
Overall	3.42	Moderate

The data revealed that the overall mean of academic procrastination, as reported by mathematics education students, had a total mean score of 3.42 with a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This suggests that the level of academic procrastination of mathematics education students was sometimes observed.

Further, the highest mean score among the indicators is 3.58 which belongs to the indicator core procrastination. This, therefore, corresponds to a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the level of self-compassion of mathematics education students in terms of core procrastination was oftentimes observed.

Furthermore, the lowest mean score among the indicators is 3.33 which belongs to the indicator work disconnection. This, therefore, indicates a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This means that the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students in terms of work disconnection is compassion among mathematics education students in terms of work disconnection was sometimes observed.

Lastly, the indicator of poor time management garnered a mean score of 3.35, which also corresponds to a descriptive equivalent of moderate. This indicates that the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students, with a focus on poor time management, was sometimes observed and consistently considered to be of moderate level.

Significant Relationship Between Parenting Styles and Academic Procrastination

Table 17 presents the result of the significant relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination, $r(150) = .351, p < .001$. Since the p-value ($p < .001$) is less than the 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is being rejected. This means that there is a positive and significant relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination.

Table 17. Significant Relationship Between Parenting Styles and Academic Procrastination

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Parenting Styles	3.79	.351	<.001	Ho Rejected
Academic Procrastination	3.42			

Significant Relationship Between Self-Compassion and Academic Procrastination

Table 17 presents the result of the significant relationship between parenting styles and academic procrastination, $r(150) = .389, p < .001$. Since the p-value is less than 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is being rejected. This means that there is a positive and significant relationship between self-compassion and academic procrastination.

Table 18. Significant Relationship Between Self-Compassion and Academic Procrastination

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Self-Compassion	3.96	.389	<.001	Ho Rejected
Academic Procrastination	3.42			

Domain/s of Parenting Styles that Significantly Influence the Academic Procrastination of Mathematics Education Students

Presented in Table 19 are the domains of parenting styles that can considerably influence the level of academic procrastination of mathematics education students. The results showed that authoritarian parenting ($\beta = .231, p < .001$) and permissive parenting ($\beta = .253, p < .001$) are the domains of parenting styles that appear to be statistically significant predictors of academic procrastination. At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. The beta value indicates that for every one-unit increase in authoritarian parenting, the level of academic procrastination will also increase by 0.231 units and for every unit increase in permissive parenting, the level of academic procrastination will also increase by 0.253 units.

Furthermore, the p-value for the remaining domain, authoritative parenting ($\beta = -.157, p = .118$), appeared to be not a statistically significant predictor of academic procrastination of mathematics education students. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-value of authoritative parenting exceeded 0.05. This means that the domain is not likely to have any effect on the academic procrastination of students.

Moreover, parenting styles explained a significant proportion of variance in academic procrastination $R^2 = .179, F = 10.740, p < .001$. The R^2 of 0.179 shows that the model predicts 17.9% of the statistical variation observed in the level of academic procrastination among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation, which is 82.1%, points to the extent to which other variables may explain the variance observed in the level of student satisfaction among the respondents.

Table 19. Domain/s of Parenting Styles that Significantly Affect Academic Procrastination Among Mathematics Education Students

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error			
Parenting Styles					
(Constant)	3.424	0.064			
Authoritative	-0.157	0.1	-0.132	.118	H0 Accepted
Authoritarian	0.231	0.081	0.273	.005	H0 Rejected
Permissive	0.253	0.099	0.247	.012	H0 Rejected
Dependent Variable:					
Academic Procrastination					

Note: $R = 0.423, R^2 = 0.179, F\text{-ratio} = 10.740, P\text{-value} = < .001$

Domain/s of Self-Compassion that Significantly Influence the Academic Procrastination of Mathematics Education Students

Presented in Table 20 is the significant influence of the domains of parenting styles on the level of academic procrastination of mathematics education students. The results showed that self-kindness ($\beta = -.293, p < .001$), isolation ($\beta = .286, p < .001$), and over-identification ($\beta = .231, p < .001$) are the domains of self-compassion that appear to be a statistically significant predictor of academic procrastination. At 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected. The beta value indicates that for every one-unit increase in self-kindness, the level of academic procrastination will also decrease by -0.293 units. Likewise, for every one-unit increase in isolation, the level of academic procrastination will increase by 0.286 units, and for every unit increase of over-identification, the level of academic procrastination will also increase by 0.231 units.

Furthermore, the p-values for the remaining domains, self-judgment ($\beta = -.114, p = .291$), common humanity ($\beta = .095, p = .496$), and mindfulness ($\beta = .029, p = .782$), appeared to be not statistically significant predictors of academic procrastination of mathematics education students. At 0.05 level of significance, the p-values of self-judgment, common humanity, and mindfulness exceeded 0.05. This means that the domains are not likely to have any effect on the academic procrastination of students.

Table 20. *Domain/s of Self-Compassion that Significantly Affect Academic Procrastination Among Mathematics Education Students*

Independent Variables	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
	Beta	Std. Error			
Self-Compassion					
(Constant)	3.424	0.064			
Self-Kindness	-0.293	0.127	-0.239	.023	H0 Rejected
Self-Judgment	0.114	0.107	0.109	.291	H0 Accepted
Common Humanity	0.095	0.139	0.075	.496	H0 Accepted
Isolation	0.286	0.101	0.292	.005	H0 Rejected
Mindfulness	0.029	0.105	0.024	.782	H0 Accepted
Over-identification	0.231	0.112	0.224	.04	H0 Rejected
Dependent Variable: Academic Procrastination					

Note: $R = 0.560$, $R^2 = 0.313$, $F\text{-ratio} = 11.014$, $P\text{-value} < .001$

Moreover, self-compassion explained a significant proportion of variance in academic procrastination, $R^2 = .313$, $F = 11.014$, $p < .001$. The R^2 of 0.313 shows that the model predicts 31.3% of the statistical variation observed in the level of academic procrastination among the respondents. The coefficient of alienation, which is 68.7%, points to the extent to which other variables may explain the variance observed in the level of student satisfaction among the respondents.

Conclusions

Drawing upon the results, conclusions were formulated in response to the questions posed in the preceding chapter. The respondents consistently reported a significant prevalence of parenting styles, indicating that students oftentimes observe this variable.

Based on the parenting styles as perceived by students, it was determined to be high. This means that the students often observe the presence of the variable. Moreover, based on the result of the self-compassion of the students, it can also be drawn that the level of self-compassion among mathematics education students was high. This means that the students often manifest the variable. In addition, the students were assessed on the level of their academic procrastination, and it was determined as moderate. This means that the academic procrastination of mathematics education students is sometimes manifested.

Furthermore, the correlation between parenting styles and academic procrastination revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study shows that parenting styles have a positive and significant relationship with academic procrastination among mathematics education students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

In addition, the correlation between self-compassion and academic procrastination also revealed a significant relationship between the two variables. The study also shows that self-compassion has a moderate, positive, and significant relationship with academic procrastination among mathematics education students. This means that the first null hypothesis proposed in the study is rejected.

Based on the result of regression analysis, in parenting styles, two domains have shown significant influence on academic procrastination. This means that the domains — authoritarian and permissive parenting styles — are significant predictors of academic procrastination in mathematics education students. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 17.9% of the statistical variation in the level of academic procrastination of the respondent, while the remaining 82.1% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the academic procrastination of respondents.

Lastly, the regression analysis of self-compassion has three domains that significantly influence the academic procrastination of the respondents. This means that the domains — self-kindness, isolation, and over-identification — are significant predictors of self-directed learning readiness. This also indicates the rejection of the second null hypothesis proposed in the study. Accordingly, the model describes 31.3% of the statistical variation in the level of academic procrastination of the respondent, while the remaining 68.7% refers to other variables that have not been included in the study that may also affect the academic procrastination of respondents.

The following results confirmed all the theories that this study was anchored in. First is the Pillar Theory of Baumrind (1996); according to her, a child's behavior is influenced by the parenting style they experience as they mature; she said that positive parenting leads to positive behavior while negative parenting leads to negative behavior. Authoritarian parenting and permissive parenting are generally interpreted as negative parenting, and the results of this study show that both these parenting styles have a positive and significant relationship to academic procrastination, a negative behavior. Second, we have the Social Mentality Theory supported by the Compassionate Mind Theory, both by the same theorist, Gilbert (2000 & 2009). Social Mentality Theory asserts that how others are treating you influences how you will be treating yourself and from that, Compassionate Mind Theory asserts that how you treat yourself has an impact on your behavior. The latter theory confirms the result that there is a significant relationship between self-compassion (how you treat yourself) and academic procrastination (the resulting behavior). Also, we can confirm the connection between these two theories from the result that parenting styles (how others are treating a person) have a significant relationship with academic procrastination. Lastly, the results also agreed with the Need for Achievement Theory by Atkinson (1952); this means motivation is

indeed influenced both by internal and external factors, and motivation influences performance.

Based on the results, several recommendations were made to address academic procrastination among mathematics education students:

Among the parenting styles, authoritarian parenting shows the lowest mean. However, the study also suggests that both authoritarian parenting and permissive parenting contribute to students' academic procrastination. Therefore, the researcher recommends that parents adopt a balanced parenting style. This involves setting clear guidelines and expectations while also providing warmth and support to their children. This approach promotes an environment conducive to fostering responsibility and engagement in learning, potentially reducing academic procrastination among students.

This is applicable not only to parents but also to teachers. They are encouraged to have a classroom environment that fosters a balance of responsiveness and demandingness. This involves providing clear expectations and academic standards while also offering support, encouragement, and understanding to students. By establishing a nurturing yet structured classroom atmosphere, teachers can help students feel valued, motivated, and empowered to engage actively in their learning process.

Under self-compassion, the indicator of over-identification shows the lowest mean and is also identified as a contributing factor to academic procrastination. Therefore, the researcher recommends that students adopt practices aimed at mitigating over-identification. This could involve techniques such as cultivating mindfulness, practicing self-awareness, and engaging in self-reflection exercises. Additionally, seeking social support and professional guidance from school guidance counselors may also be beneficial in developing healthier coping mechanisms and reducing the negative impact of over-identification on academic performance.

On the other hand, the indicator self-kindness exhibits the highest mean. Furthermore, the results suggest that self-kindness has a negative influence on academic procrastination, indicating that practicing self-kindness can help reduce the likelihood of procrastination among students. Therefore, the researcher encourages students to continue prioritizing self-kindness in their daily activities. This could involve engaging in self-care activities, practicing self-compassionate self-talk, and cultivating a supportive inner dialogue. By nurturing a mindset of kindness and understanding towards oneself, students can develop greater resilience, motivation, and focus in their academic pursuits.

Although students already exhibit a moderate level of work disconnection, which is an indicator of academic procrastination with the lowest mean, they are still discouraged from practicing it. The researcher emphasizes the importance of avoiding work disconnection as it hinders academic progress. Instead, students are encouraged to cultivate habits of focused attention and time management. This may involve setting clear goals, breaking tasks into manageable chunks, and establishing regular study routines. By staying actively engaged in their work and minimizing distractions, students can enhance productivity and reduce the temptation to procrastinate.

With core procrastination being the indicator showing the highest mean and at a high level, students are strongly discouraged from engaging in this behavior. This type of procrastination involves delaying important tasks, which can significantly impact academic performance and overall success. Instead, students are urged to cultivate habits that promote proactive task management and timely completion of assignments. This may involve breaking tasks into smaller, more manageable steps, setting realistic deadlines, and prioritizing tasks based on their importance and urgency. Additionally, seeking support from peers, instructors, or academic advisors can provide valuable assistance in overcoming procrastination habits.

Analyzing the results and related literature, the researcher identified several programs/interventions recommended to indirectly reduce academic procrastination tendencies among students in relation to parenting styles and self-compassion. First is a local family empowerment program and intervention designed to strengthen family functioning, promote positive parenting practices, improve communication and problem-solving skills, and enhance resilience in the face of adversity. By empowering families, communities can be more resilient, cohesive, and capable of addressing systematic issues that affect children's well-being. Second is the Mindful Self-Compassion Program for students, designed by Gilbert (2009), which focuses on cultivating self-compassion skills through mindfulness practices and guided exercises. By increasing students' ability to be kind and understanding towards themselves, this program aims to reduce self-criticism and perfectionism, which are common triggers for academic procrastination.

Moreover, it is important to understand the broad nature of academic procrastination and the different factors that contribute to it. While parenting styles and self-compassion are significant predictors of academic procrastination, other factors not included in the study may also contribute to students' tendencies to delay academic tasks. Therefore, future researchers are recommended to explore other possible predictors of academic procrastination, such as fear of failure, perfectionism, low self-efficacy and others. It is also important to note that this study used the Parental Authority Questionnaire (PAQ) in measuring parenting style, which is limited to three parenting styles and does not include the fourth parenting style, the uninvolved parenting style. Future researchers are then suggested to use a measuring tool that measures all four when measuring parenting style.

References

Abdollahi, A., Allen, K. A., & Taheri, A. (2020). Moderating the role of self-compassion in the relationship between perfectionism and depression. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, pp. 38, 459–471. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10942-020-00346-3>

- Adams, R. V., & Blair, E. (2019). Impact of time management behaviors on undergraduate engineering students' performance. *Sage Open*, 9(1), 2158244018824506. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244018824506>
- Adelson, J. L., & McCoach, D. B. (2010). Measuring the mathematical attitudes of elementary students: The effects of a 4-point or 5-point Likert-type scale. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 70(5), 796-807. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0013164410366694>
- Afzal, S., & Jami, H. (2018). Prevalence of academic procrastination and reasons for academic procrastination in university students. *Journal of Behavioural Sciences*, 28(1), 51-69. https://www.academia.edu/download/81553703/04_v28_1_18.pdf
- Ahmed, I., Bernhardt, G. V., & Shivappa, P. (2023). Prevalence of Academic Procrastination and Its Negative Impact on Students. *Biomedical and Biotechnology Research Journal (BBRJ)*, 7(3), 363-370. https://doi.org/10.4103/bbrj.bbrj_64_2
- Akhter, N., Noor, A. E., & Iqbal, S. (2020). Impact of parents' authoritative style on personality traits of children: a case study of Elementary class students in Pakistan. *Journal of Elementary Education*, 29(2), 37-50. <http://journals.pu.edu.pk/journals/index.php/jee/article/view/1616>
- Akpur, U. (2020). The Effect of Procrastination on Academic Achievement: A Meta-Analysis Study. *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, 6(4), 681-690. <https://doi.org/10.12973/ijem.6.4.681>
- Alhani, F., Asghari-Jafarabadi, M., Norouzadeh, R., Rahimi-Bashar, F., Vahedian-Azimi, A., Jamialahmadi, T., & Sahebkar, A. (2022). The effect of family-centered empowerment model on the quality of life of adults with chronic diseases: An updated systematic review and meta-analysis. *Journal of Affective Disorders*, 316, 140-147. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jad.2022.07.066>
- Altaf, S., Hassan, B., Khattak, A. Z., & Iqbal, N. (2021). Relationship of Parenting Styles with Decision-Making and Self-concept among Adolescents. *Foundation University Journal of Psychology*, 5(2). <http://fujp.fui.edu.pk/index.php/fujp/article/view/318>
- Alyami, A., Abdulwahed, A., Azhar, A., Binsaddik, A., & Bafaraj, S. M. (2021). Impact of Time-Management on the Student's Academic Performance: A Cross-Sectional Study. *Creative Education*, 12, 471-485. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ce.2021.123033>
- Amani M, Arbabi M. (2020). The Mediating Role of Academic Self-Regulation in the Relationship between Parenting Dimensions and Academic Procrastination. *Int. J. School. Health.*, 7(2), 21-29. <https://doi.org/10.30476/intjsh.2020.84983.1050>
- Anālayo, B. (2019). Adding historical depth to definitions of mindfulness. *Current opinion in psychology*, pp. 28, 11-14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2018.09.013>
- Andangsari, E. W., Djunaidi, A., Fitriana, E., & Harding, D. (2018). Loneliness and problematic internet use (piu) as causes of academic procrastination. *Int'l J. Soc. Sci. Stud.*, 6(2), 113. <https://doi.org/10.11114/ijss.v6i2.2834>
- Anderson, A. S., Watson, K. H., Reising, M. M., Dunbar, J. P., Gruhn, M. A., & Compas, B. E. (2023). Adolescents' coping and internalizing symptoms: Role of maternal socialization of coping and depression symptoms. *Mental health & prevention*, 30, 200270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mhp.2023.200270>
- Arnold, I. J. (2023). The link between procrastination and graduation rates: evidence from the ALEKS learning platform. *Education Economics*, 31(3), 275-287. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/09645292.2022.2063796>
- Atkinson, J. W. (1957). Motivational determinants of risk-taking behavior. *Psychological Review*, pp. 64, 359-372. <https://psycnet.apa.org/journals/rev/64/6p1/359/>
- Baten, E., Vansteenkiste, M., De Muyne, G. J., De Poortere, E., & Desoete, A. (2020). How can the blow of math difficulty on elementary school children's motivational, cognitive, and affective experiences be dampened? The critical role of autonomy-supportive instructions. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(8), 1490. <https://psycnet.apa.org/fulltext/2019-78955-001.html>
- Batool, S. S. (2020). Academic achievement: Interplay of positive parenting, self-esteem, and academic procrastination. *Australian Journal of Psychology*, 72(2), 174-187. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajpy.12280>
- Baumrind, D. (1966). Effects of authoritative parental control on child behavior. *Child Development*, 37(4), 887-907. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/1126611>
- Bi, X., Yang, Y., Li, H., Wang, M., Zhang, W., & Deater-Deckard, K. (2018). Parenting styles and parent-adolescent relationships: The mediating roles of behavioral autonomy and parental authority. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 2187. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02187>
- Bowlby, J. (1944). Forty-four Juvenile Thieves: Their Characters and Home Life. *The International Journal of Psychoanalysis*, pp. 25, 19-53. <https://awspntest.apa.org/record/1945-00751-001>
- Brignardello, M., & Paniagua, A. (2023). Dimensional Structure of MAPS-15: Validation of the Multidimensional Academic Procrastination Scale. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 3201 (20), 14-15. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20043201>

- Bruk, A., Scholl, S. G., & Bless, H. (2022). You and I both: Self-compassion reduces self–other differences in evaluation of showing vulnerability. *Personality and Social Psychology Bulletin*, 48(7), 1054–1067. <https://doi.org/10.1177/01461672211031080>
- Buri, J. (1991). Parental Authority Questionnaire. *Journal of Personality Assessment*, 57(1), 110–119. https://doi.org/10.1207/s15327752jpa5701_13
- Caballero, C., Scherer, E., West, M. R., Mrazek, M. D., Gabrieli, C. F., & Gabrieli, J. D. (2019). Greater mindfulness is associated with better academic achievement in middle school. *Mind, Brain, and Education*, 13(3), 157-166. <https://doi.org/10.1111/mbe.12200>
- Caratıquit, K. D., & Caratıquit, L. J. C. (2023). Influence of social media addiction on academic achievement in distance learning: Intervening role of academic procrastination. *Turkish Online Journal of Distance Education*, 24(1), 1-19. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/tojde/issue/74274/1060563>
- Chio, F. H., Mak, W. W., & Ben, C. L. (2021). Meta-analytic review on the differential effects of self-compassion components on well-being and psychological distress: The moderating role of dialecticism on self-compassion. *Clinical Psychology Review*, p. 85, 101986. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpr.2021.101986>
- Chishima, Y., Mizuno, M., Sugawara, D., & Miyagawa, Y. (2018). The influence of self-compassion on cognitive appraisals and coping with stressful events. *Mindfulness*, 9(6), 1907-1915. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-018-0933-0>
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches* (4th ed.). SAGE Publications. <http://www.ceil-conicet.gov.ar/wp-content/uploads/2015/10/Creswell-Cap-10.pdf>
- Cucu Ciuhan, G. (2021). Relationship between permissive parenting style and atypical behavior in preschool children, with generalized anxiety as mediator. *Early Child Development and Care*, 1-9. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/03004430.2021.2017908>
- De Muynck, G. J., Morbée, S., Soenens, B., Haerens, L., Vermeulen, O., Vande Broek, G., & Vansteenkiste, M. (2021). Do both coaches and parents contribute to youth soccer players' motivation and engagement? An examination of their unique (de) motivating roles. *International Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 19(5), 761-779. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1612197X.2020.1739111>
- Denzin, N. K., & Lincoln, Y. S. (Eds.). (2011). *The Sage handbook of qualitative research*. Sage. <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=AIRpMHgBYqIC&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&dq=denzin+and+lincoln+2011&ots=kqBNDFlBi9&sig=e5VSITldPgmKuZukpl1zAfCNYtk>
- Dewi, R. K., & Sumarni, S. (2023). Parenting style and family empowerment for children's growth and development: a systematic review. *Journal of Public Health in Africa*, 14(sZ). <https://doi.org/10.4081/jphia.2023.2582>
- Dokukina, P. (2022). Comparing Effects of Loving-Kindness Meditation and Watching a Nature Movie on Positive Emotions and Social Connectedness: An Online Qualtrics Study. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1642309/FULLTEXT01.pdf>
- Domingo, K. (2023). Factors Influencing Academic Procrastination Habits among Grade 12 Humanities and Social Sciences Students at Lal-lo National High School. *The Quester: Lal-lo National High School Research Journal*, 1(1), 38–54. <https://thequester.deped-lallonhs.com/index.php/home/article/view/3>
- Dreisoerner, A., Junker, N. M., & Van Dick, R. (2021). The relationship among the components of self-compassion: A pilot study using a compassionate writing intervention to enhance self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 22, 21-47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-019-00217-4>
- Dreisoerner, A., Junker, N. M., & Van Dick, R. (2021). The relationship among the components of self-compassion: A pilot study using a compassionate writing intervention to enhance self-kindness, common humanity, and mindfulness. *Journal of Happiness Studies*, 22, 21-47. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10902-019-00217-4>
- Egan, H., & Mantzios, M. (2018). A qualitative exploration of self-kindness and “treating oneself” in contexts of eating, weight regulation and other health behaviors: implications for mindfulness-based eating programs. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 9, 377424. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2018.00880>
- Egan, H., O'Hara, M., Cook, A., & Mantzios, M. (2022). Mindfulness, self-compassion, resiliency and wellbeing in higher education: a recipe to increase academic performance. *Journal of Further and Higher Education*, 46(3), 301–311. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0309877X.2021.1912306>
- Einabad, Z. S., Roshan, F. J., Roshan, R., & Ghasemzadeh, M. (2019). The Relationship Among Mindfulness, Acceptance, and Academic Procrastination in Students. *Zahedan Journal of Research in Medical Sciences*, 21(4). <https://doi.org/10.5812/zjrms.68450>
- Esmailian, N., Dehghani, M., Dehghani, Z., & Lee, J. (2018). Mindfulness-based cognitive therapy enhances emotional resiliency in children with divorced parents. *Mindfulness*, 9, 1052-1062. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-017-0840-9>
- Febiyanti, A., & Rachmawati, Y. (2021, March). Is authoritative parenting the best parenting style? In 5th International Conference on

- Early Childhood Education (ICECE 2020) (pp. 94-99). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.210322.021>
- Fentaw, Y., Moges, B. T., & Ismail, S. M. (2022). Academic procrastination behavior among public university students. *Education Research International*, 2022(1), 1277866. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/1277866>
- Gamst-Klaussen, T., Steel, P., & Svartdal, F. (2019). Procrastination and personal finances: Exploring the roles of planning and financial self-efficacy. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 10, 442909. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00775>
- Garcia, O. F., Lopez-Fernandez, O., & Serra, E. (2021). Raising Spanish children with an antisocial tendency: Do we know what the optimal parenting style is? *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 36(13-14), 6117-6144.
- Garcia, O. F., Lopez-Fernandez, O., & Serra, E. (2021). Raising Spanish children with an antisocial tendency: Do we know what the optimal parenting style is? *Journal of interpersonal violence*, 36(13-14), 6117-6144. <https://doi.org/10.1177/088626051881842>
- Gedik, Z. (2019). Self-compassion and health-promoting lifestyle behaviors in college students. *Psychology, health & medicine*, 24(1), 108-114. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13548506.2018.1503692>
- Germer, C., Germer, C. K., & Neff, K. (2019). *Teaching the mindful self-compassion program: A guide for professionals*. Guilford Publications. <https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=FqOdDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PP1&ots=VhaCiEUcc4&sig=1C7FrHPjaqZ0qJQtUoOyVSZf-oc>
- Gezgin, D. M. (2021). Gender, Self-regulation, Academic Procrastination, and Smartphone Checking Frequency During Study Hours in Predicting Turkish Adolescents' Smartphone Addiction. *Addicta: The Turkish Journal on Addictions*, 9(1), 38-47. <https://doi.org/10.5152/ADDICTA.2021.21027>
- Gilbert, P. (2009). *The Compassionate Mind: A New Approach to Life's Challenges*. Constable, 26, 592. <https://lib.ugent.be/catalog/rug01:002040613>
- Gilbert, Paul. (2000). Social mentalities: Internal 'social' conflicts and the role of inner warmth and compassion in cognitive therapy. *Genes on the couch: Explorations in evolutionary psychotherapy*, 118-150. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2001-16368-006>
- Gimbel, N. M. (2023). *An Examination of the Self-Compassion Component of Isolation as Experienced by People With Chronic Pain* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Georgia). <https://search.proquest.com/openview/7e46b9e92858bd7c27aeda2dd8c5a99c/1?pq-origsite=scholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Golden, H. L., Vosper, J., Kingston, J., & Ellett, L. (2021). The impact of mindfulness-based programmes on self-compassion in nonclinical populations: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Mindfulness*, 12, 29-52. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-020-01501-8>
- Golpour, R., Amini, Z. M., Kasraie, S., & Senobar, L. (2015). The role of self-compassion components on prediction procrastination and depression in students. *Journal of educational and management studies*, 5(4), 204-210. [http://jems.science-line.com/attachments/article/34/J.%20Educ.%20Manage.%20Stud.,%205\(4\)%20204-210,%202015.pdf](http://jems.science-line.com/attachments/article/34/J.%20Educ.%20Manage.%20Stud.,%205(4)%20204-210,%202015.pdf)
- Gong, X., & McBride-Chang, C. (2015). Role of parenting styles and child's sex in academic engagement and pro-social behavior among Chinese elementary school children. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 24(9), 2680-2691.
- Gonzalez, A., Holbein, M. F. D., & Quilter, S. (2018). Parenting and educational achievement: Intervening processes between parental involvement and children's academic performance. *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 80(5), 1244-1259.
- Grund, A., & Fries, S. (2018). Understanding procrastination: A motivational approach. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 121, 120-130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2017.09.035>
- Hagerman, L. A., Manankil-Rankin, L., & Schwind, J. K. (2020). Self-compassion in undergraduate nursing: an integrative review. *International journal of nursing education scholarship*, 17(1), 20200021. <https://doi.org/10.1515/ijnes-2020-0021>
- Hajiazizi, A., & Ho, R. (2015). The relationship between self-compassion and academic procrastination being mediated by shame and anxiety. *The International Journal of Indian Psychology*, Forthcoming. https://papers.ssrn.com/Sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=2703405
- Hayat, A. A., Jahanian, M., Bazrafcan, L., & Shokrpour, N. (2020). Prevalence of academic procrastination among medical students and its relationship with their academic achievement. *Shiraz E-Medical Journal*, 21(7). <https://doi.org/10.5812/semj.96049>
- Hayek, J., Schneider, F., Lahoud, N., Tueni, M., & de Vries, H. (2022). Authoritative parenting stimulates academic achievement, also partly via self-efficacy and intention towards getting good grades. *Plos one*, 17(3), e0265595. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265595>
- <https://doi.org/10.1177/0886260518818426>
- Inam, A., Fatima, H., Naeem, H., Mujeeb, H., Khatoon, R., Wajahat, T., ... & Sher, F. (2021). Self-compassion and empathy as

predictors of happiness among late adolescents. *Social Sciences*, 10(10), 380. <https://doi.org/10.3390/socsci10100380>

Johansson, F., Rozental, A., Edlund, K., Côté, P., Sundberg, T., Onell, C., ... & Skillgate, E. (2023). Associations between procrastination and subsequent health outcomes among university students in Sweden. *JAMA network open*, 6(1), e2249346-e2249346. <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2022.49346>

Joseph, O., Hasbullah, M., & Arshat, Z. (2021). A Review of Literature on Parenting Styles, Parental Competence and Emotional Intelligence among College Students. *Medico Legal Update*, 21(2), 901–908. <https://doi.org/10.37506/mlu.v21i2.2798>

Juwono, I. D., Kun, B., Demetrovics, Z., & Urbán, R. (2023). Healthy and unhealthy dimensions of perfectionism: Perfectionism and mental health in Hungarian adults. *International Journal of Mental Health and Addiction*, 21(5), 3017-3032. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s11469-022-00771-8>

Kabat-Zinn, J. (2003). Mindfulness-based interventions in context: past, present, and future. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2003-03824-002>

Kim, Y., Calzada, E. J., Barajas-Gonzalez, R. G., Huang, K. Y., Brotman, L. M., Castro, A., & Pichardo, C. (2018). The role of authoritative and authoritarian parenting in the early academic achievement of Latino students. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 110(1), 119. <https://doi.org/10.1037/edu0000192>

Kroshus, E., Hawrilenko, M., & Browning, A. (2021). Stress, self-compassion, and well-being during the transition to college. *Social Science & Medicine*, 269, 113514. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2020.113514>

Kuftyak, E. (2022). Procrastination, stress and academic performance in students. *Arpha Proceedings*, 5, 965-974. <https://ap.pensoft.net/article/24340/download/pdf>

Kuppens, S., & Ceulemans, E. (2019). Parenting styles: A closer look at a well-known concept. *Journal of child and family studies*, 28(1), 168-181. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s10826-018-1242-x%23ref-CR3>

Kurtovic, A., Vrdoljak, G., & Idzanovic, A. (2019). Predicting procrastination: The role of academic achievement, self-efficacy and perfectionism. *International Journal of Educational Psychology: Ijep*, 8(1), 1-26. <https://dialnet.unirioja.es/servlet/articulo?codigo=7447499>

Lao, H., Lao, K. G., Lao, K. A., Santos, M. D., & Alieto, E. (2023, April). Due Monday, Do Monday: A Qualitative Study of Academic Procrastination Among Undergraduate Students During the Pandemic. In 19th International Conference of the Asia Association of Computer-Assisted Language Learning (AsiaCALL, 2022) (pp. 197-221). https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=tAm4EAAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PA197&dq=due+monday+do+monday+lao+et+al&ots=GITuNcPX4p&sig=IhL1lR93n6Y6dXUjMjGrvV_sRAI

Lavrič, M., & Naterer, A. (2020). The power of authoritative parenting: A cross-national study of effects of exposure to different parenting styles on life satisfaction. *Children and Youth Services Review*, 116, 105274. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.childyouth.2020.105274>

Lazarus, R. S. (1984). *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. Springer. [https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=i-ySQQUpr8C&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Lazarus,+R.+S.,+and+Folkman,+S.+\(1984\).+Stress,+Appraisal,+and+Coping.+New+York:+Springer.&ots=DhEPprdiTf&sig=pG7UnmlWkBif-eZt5VpMR1AJ1AU](https://books.google.com/books?hl=en&lr=&id=i-ySQQUpr8C&oi=fnd&pg=PR5&dq=Lazarus,+R.+S.,+and+Folkman,+S.+(1984).+Stress,+Appraisal,+and+Coping.+New+York:+Springer.&ots=DhEPprdiTf&sig=pG7UnmlWkBif-eZt5VpMR1AJ1AU)

Leary, M. R., Tate, E. B., Adams, C. E., Batts Allen, A., & Hancock, J. (2007). Self-compassion and reactions to unpleasant self-relevant events: the implications of treating oneself kindly. *Journal of personality and social psychology*, 92(5), 887. <https://psycnet.apa.org/fulltext/2007-06231-009.html>

Leppma, M., & Darrah, M. (2024). Self-efficacy, mindfulness, and self-compassion as predictors of math anxiety in undergraduate students. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 55(4), 883-898. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2022.2054740>

Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of psychology*. <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1933-01885-001>

Lin, J. W., & Mai, L. J. (2018). Impact of mindfulness meditation intervention on academic performance. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 55(3), 366-375. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2016.1231617>

Ling, D., Petrakis, M., Olver, J. (2021). The Use of Common Humanity Scenarios to Promote Compassion in Healthcare Workers. *Australian Social Work*, 74(1), 110-121. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/344294942_The_Use_of_Common_Humanity_Scenarios_to_Promote_Compassion_in_Healthcare_Workers

Ling, G., Elliot, N., Burstein, J. C., McCaffrey, D. F., MacArthur, C. A., & Holtzman, S. (2021). Writing motivation: A validation

- study of self-judgment and performance. *Assessing Writing*, p. 48, 100509. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.asw.2020.100509>
- Liu, J., Xiao, B., Hipson, W. E., Coplan, R. J., Yang, P., & Cheah, C. S. (2018). Self-regulation, learning problems, and maternal authoritarian parenting in Chinese children: A developmental cascades model. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, pp. 27, 4060–4070. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-018-1218-x>
- Loke, H., & Low, C. (2021). Relationship between parenting style, psychological well-being and academic performance among university students. December, pp. 0–12. <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Hui-Lin-Loke/publication/357074163>
- López, A., Sanderman, R., & Schroevers, M. J. (2018). A close examination of the relationship between self-compassion and depressive symptoms. *Mindfulness*, 9, 1470-1478. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-018-0891-6>
- Lorence, B., Hidalgo, V., Pérez-Padilla, J., & Menéndez, S. (2019). The Role of Parenting Styles on Behavior Problem Profiles of Adolescents. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(15), 2767. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16152767>
- Lowell, E. L. (1952). The effect of need for achievement on learning and speed of performance. *Journal of Psychology*, pp. 33, 31–40. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/pdf/10.1080/00223980.1952.9712815>
- Ma, Y., Siu, A., & Tse, W. S. (2018). The role of high parental expectations in Adolescents' academic performance and Depression in Hong Kong. *Journal of Family Issues*, 39(9), 2505-2522. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0192513X1875519>
- Marsh, I. C., Chan, S. W., & MacBeth, A. (2018). Self-compassion and psychological distress in adolescents—a meta-analysis. *Mindfulness*, pp. 9, 1011–1027. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-017-0850-7>
- Metin, U. B., Peeters, M. C., & Taris, T. W. (2018). Correlates of procrastination and performance at work: The role of having “good fit”. *Journal of Prevention & Intervention in the Community*, 46(3), 228-244. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/10852352.2018.1470187>
- Mikaeili, N., & Salmani, A. (2021). Investigating the role of parenting styles in predicting students' academic procrastination. *Journal of Family Relations Studies*, 1(1), 13-20. <https://doi.org/10.22098/JHRS.2022.8669.1002>
- Mikaeili, N., & Salmani, A. (2021). Investigating the role of parenting styles in predicting students' academic procrastination. *Journal of Family Relations Studies*, 1(1), 13-20. <https://doi.org/10.22098/JHRS.2022.8669.1002>
- Mowen, T. J., & Schroeder, R. D. (2018). Maternal parenting style and delinquency by race and the moderating effect of structural disadvantage. *Youth & Society*, 50(2), 139-159. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0044118X1559802>
- Muris, P., & Otgaar, H. (2020). The process of science: A critical evaluation of more than 15 years of research on self-compassion with the Self-Compassion Scale. *Mindfulness*, 11, 1469-1482. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-020-01363-0>
- Nartea, M., Gabriel, M., Samala, H. R., & Javier, R. (2020). Millennials procrastination: Factors and its relation to academic performance. *Asia Pacific Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 8(3), 107-114. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mecmack-Nartea/publication/343064526_Millennial's_Procrastination_Factors_and_its_Relation_to_Academic_Performance/links/5f154bd0a6fdcc3ed718b173/Millennials-Procrastination-Factors-and-its-Relation-to-Academic-Performance.pdf
- Nayak, S. G. (2019). Impact of Procrastination and Time-Management on Academic Stress among Undergraduate Nursing Students: A Cross-Sectional Study. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 12(3). https://internationaljournalofcaringsciences.org/docs/18_nayak_original_12_3.pdf
- Neff, K. (2003). The Development and Validation of a Scale to Measure Self-Compassion. *Psychology Press series*, 1554 (2), 223–250. <http://doi.org/10.1080/15298860390209035>
- Neff, K. (2022). Self-Compassion: Theory, Method, Research, and Intervention. *Annual Reviews of Psychology*. (74), pp. 193–218. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-psych-032420-031047>
- Neff, K. D. (2023). Self-compassion: Theory, method, research, and intervention. *Annual review of psychology*, 74(1), 193–218. <https://www.annualreviews.org/content/journals/10.1146/annurev-psych-032420-031047>
- Neff, K. D., Long, P., Knox, M. C., Davidson, O., Kuchar, A., Costigan, A., ... & Breines, J. G. (2018). The forest and the trees: Examining the association of self-compassion and its positive and negative components with psychological functioning. *Self and identity*, 17(6), 627-645. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15298868.2018.1436587>
- Nollora, A. M. (2022). Career Motivation, Distance Learning Attitude, and Time Management of the Offshore Graduate School Students of a Philippine Public University. *International Journal of Arts, Sciences and Education*, 3(4), 112-123. <http://www.mail.ijase.org/index.php/ijase/article/view/194>
- Oehler, R. (2024). Attachment to Diagnostic Labels: Social Media, Over Identification, and Self-Efficacy for Personal Recovery. https://scholar.umw.edu/student_research/579/

- Olla, M. B., Daulima, N. H. C., & Putri, Y. S. E. (2018). The experience of parents implementing authoritarian parenting for their school-age children. *Enfermeria clinica*, 28, 122-125. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1130-8621\(18\)30050-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1130-8621(18)30050-0)
- Onwuegbuzie, A. J., & Jiao, Q. G. (2018). I will Go to the Library Later: The Relationship Between Academic Procrastination and Library Anxiety. *College & Research Libraries*, 61(1), 45–54. <https://doi.org/10.5860/crl.61.1.45>
- Opiyo, P. O., Aloka, D. P. J., Raburu, P. A., & Aomo, J. A. (2018). Relationship between permissive parenting style and examination cheating tendencies among Kenya secondary school students. *International Journal of Advanced Scientific and Technical Research*, 1. <https://doi.org/10.2478/mjss-2018-0064>
- Özberk, E. H., & Kurtça, T. T. (2021). Profiles of academic procrastination in higher education: A cross-cultural study using latent profile analysis. *International Journal of Psychology and Educational Studies*, 8(3), 150-160. <https://dergipark.org.tr/en/pub/pes/issue/64305/976311>
- Ozmat, E. E., Martin, J. L., & Cimini, M. D. (2024). Self-Judgment and Depression Among Students of Color During the Transition to College: Gender Differences. *Journal of College Student Retention: Research, Theory & Practice*, 15210251241230077. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1521025124123007>
- Pang, D., & Ruch, W. (2019). Fusing character strengths and mindfulness interventions: Benefits for job satisfaction and performance. *Journal of Occupational Health Psychology*, 24(1), 150. <https://doi.org/10.1037/ocp0000144>
- Pinquart, M., & Gerke, D. C. (2019). Associations of parenting styles with self-esteem in children and adolescents: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 28, 2017-2035. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-019-01417-5>
- Pinxten, M., De Laet, T., Van Soom, C., Peeters, C., & Langie, G. (2019). Purposeful delay and academic achievement. A critical review of the Active Procrastination Scale. *Learning and Individual Differences*, 73, 42-51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lindif.2019.04.010>
- Pirzadeh Nouri, N., Asheghi, M., Asheghi, M., & Hesari, M. (2021). Mediation Role of Emotion Regulation Between Procrastination, Psychological Wellbeing, and Life Satisfaction in the Elderly. *Practice in Clinical Psychology*, 9(2), 111-120. https://jpcp.uswr.ac.ir/browse.php?a_id=726&sid=1&slc_lang=en&html=1
- Prime, H., Wade, M., & Browne, D. T. (2020). Risk and resilience in family well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic. *American Psychologist*, 75(5), 631-643. <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000660>
- Qian, L., & Fuqiang, Z. (2018). Academic stress, academic procrastination and academic performance: A moderated dual-mediation model. *Journal of Innovation and Sustainability RISUS*, 9(2), 38–46. <https://doi.org/10.24212/2179-3565.2018v9i2p38-46>
- Rabin, L. A., Fogel, J., & Nutter-Upham, K. E. (2019). Academic Procrastination in College Students: The Role of Self-reported Executive Function. *Journal of Clinical and Experimental Neuropsychology*, 33(3), 344–357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13803395.2010.518597>
- Rahmandani, A., & Salma, S. (2021). Will self-compassion relieve distress?: A correlational study among Indonesian undergraduate students. *Yonago Acta Medica*, 64(2), 192-199. <https://doi.org/10.33160/yam.2021.05.013>
- Rashid, A., Sharif, I., Khan, S., & Malik, F. (2020). Relationship between time management behavior and academic performance of university students. *Journal of Business and Social Review in Emerging Economies*, 6(4), 1497–1504. <https://doi.org/10.26710/jbsee.v6i4.1481>
- Reizer, A. (2019). Bringing Self-Kindness Into the Workplace: Exploring the Mediating Role of Self-Compassion in the Associations Between Attachment and Organizational Outcomes. *Front. Psychol.* 10:1148. doi 10.3389/fpsyg.2019.01148
- Ren, Y., Chi, X., Bu, H., Huang, L., Wang, S., Zhang, Y., Bu, H., Zeng, D., Shan, H., & Jiao, C. (2023). Warm and harsh parenting, self-kindness and self-judgment, and well-being: An examination of developmental differences in a large sample of adolescents. *Children*, 10(2), 406. <https://doi.org/10.3390/children10020406>
- Rizka, S. M., & Bacotang, J. B. (2019). The relationship between parenting styles and children’s social skills. *International conference on early childhood education*, pp. 258-262. <https://jurnal.usk.ac.id/ICECED/article/view/13704>
- Roster, C. A., & Ferrari, J. R. (2020). Time is on my side—Or is it? Assessing how perceived control of time and procrastination influence emotional exhaustion on the job. *Behavioral Sciences*, 10(6), 98. <https://doi.org/10.3390/bs10060098>
- Ruiz-Hernández, J. A., Moral-Zafra, E., Llor-Esteban, B., & Jiménez-Barbero, J. A. (2018). Influence of parental styles and other psychosocial variables on the development of externalizing behaviors in adolescents: A systematic review. *European Journal of Psychology Applied to Legal Context*, 11(1), 9-21. https://journals.copmadrid.org/ejpalc/archivos/1889_1861_ejpalc_11_1_0009.pdf
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2002). Overview of self-determination theory: An organismic dialectical perspective. *Handbook of self-determination research*, 2, 3-33. <http://www.kopiloht.de/sdthb..pdf>

- Saltürk, A. (2022). A qualitative study among self-identified perfectionists and procrastinators in academic tasks. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(2), 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.17275/per.22.26.9.2>
- Sanjeevan, D., & de Zoysa, P. (2018). The association of parenting style on depression, anxiety and stress among Tamil speaking adolescents in the Colombo city. *Sri Lanka Journal of Child Health*, 47(4), 342-347. <https://doi.org/10.4038/sljch.v47i4.8597>
- Santini, Z. I., Jose, P. E., Cornwell, E. Y., Koyanagi, A., Nielsen, L., Hinrichsen, C., ... & Koushede, V. (2020). Social disconnectedness, perceived isolation, and symptoms of depression and anxiety among older Americans (NSHAP): a longitudinal mediation analysis. *The Lancet Public Health*, 5(1), e62-e70. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667\(19\)30230-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2468-2667(19)30230-0)
- Sapancı, A. (2021). The Mediating Role of Self-Compassion in the Relationship Between Perfectionism and Academic Procrastination in Pre-service Teachers. *Journal of Pedagogical Research*, 5(4), 214–229. <https://doi.org/10.33902/JPR.2021474638>
- Sapancı, A., & Güler, A. (2021). The Mediating Role of Metacognitive Processes in the Relationship between Personality Traits and Academic Achievement of University Students. *Sakarya University Journal of Education*, 11(3), 501-525. <https://doi.org/10.19126/suje.974304>
- Sederlund, A., R. Burns, L., & Rogers, W. (2020). Multidimensional models of perfectionism and procrastination: seeking determinants of both. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(14), 5099. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17145099>
- Seeram, E. (2019). An overview of correlational research. *Radiologic Technology*, 91(2), 176–179. <http://www.radiologictechnology.org/content/91/2/176.short>
- Shabbir, F., & Ishaq, K. (2019). Impact of Perceived Parenting Styles and Emotional Intelligence on Communication Competence among Adolescents. *ARC Journal of Psychiatry*, 4(3), 1–21. <http://surl.li/qjpnz>
- Shin, N. Y., & Lim, Y. J. (2019). Contribution of self-compassion to positive mental health among Korean university students. *International Journal of Psychology*, 54(6), 800–806. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijop.12527>
- Siegel, J. A., Huellemann, K. L., Hillier, C. C., & Campbell, L. (2020). The protective role of self-compassion for women’s positive body image: An open replication and extension. *Body Image*, 32, 136-144. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bodyim.2019.12.003>
- Sirois, F. M., Stride, C. B., & Pychyl, T. A. (2023). Procrastination and health: A longitudinal test of the roles of stress and health behaviors. *British Journal of Health Psychology*, 28(3), 860-875. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjhp.12658>
- Skinner, E. A., Edge, K., Altman, J., & Sherwood, H. (2003). Searching for the structure of coping: a review and critique of category systems for classifying ways of coping. *Psychological bulletin*, 129(2), 216. <https://psycnet.apa.org/fulltext/2003-01977-005.html>
- Smetana, J. G., & Rote, W. M. (2019). Adolescent–parent relationships: Progress, processes, and prospects. *Annual Review of Developmental Psychology*, 1, 41-68. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-devpsych-121318-084903>
- Stallman, H. M., Ohan, J. L., & Chiera, B. (2018). The role of social support, being present and self-kindness in university student well-being. *British Journal of Guidance & Counselling*, 46(4), 365-374. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03069885.2017.1343458>
- Steel, P., Taras, D., Ponak, A., & Kammeyer-Mueller, J. (2022). Self-regulation of slippery deadlines: the role of procrastination in work performance. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 783789. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2021.783789>
- Steele, E., & McKinney, C. (2018). Emerging Adult Psychological Problems and Parenting Style: Moderation by Parent-child Relationship Quality. *Personality and Individual Differences*. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2018.04.048>
- Sulaiman, F., & Hassan, M. M. (2019). A pilot study of the relationship between parenting style and academic procrastination among final-year students of the Faculty of Human Ecology, Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM). *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (MJSSH)*, 4(7), 152-167. <https://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v4i7.314>
- Sulaiman, F., & Hassan, M. M. (2019). A pilot study of the relationship between parenting style and academic procrastination among final-year students of the Faculty of Human Ecology, Universiti Putra Malaysia (UPM). *Malaysian Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities (MJSSH)*, 4(7), 152-167. <https://doi.org/10.47405/mjssh.v4i7.314>
- Sullivan, G. M., & Artino Jr, A. R. (2013). Analyzing and interpreting data from Likert-type scales. *Journal of graduate medical education*, 5(4), 541–542. <https://doi.org/10.4300/JGME-5-4-18>
- Sumanasekera, I., Hamid, J. A., Khatibi, A., & Azam, S. F. (2021). Review of Literature on Involvement and Style of Parents Towards Student Performance. *International Journal of Advanced Scientific and Technical Research*, 1, 26-38. <https://doi.org/10.26808/rs.st.11v1.03>
- Sumaya, I. C., & Darling, E. (2018). Procrastination, flow, and academic performance in real-time using the experience sampling method. *The Journal of Genetic Psychology*, 179(3), 123-131. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00221325.2018.1449097>

- Taylor, S. B., Kennedy, L. A., Lee, C. E., & Waller, E. K. (2022). Common humanity in the classroom: Increasing self-compassion and coping self-efficacy through a mindfulness-based intervention. *Journal of American College Health*, 70(1), 142–149. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/07448481.2020.1728278>
- Türel, Y. K., & Dokumaci, O. (2022). Use of media and technology, academic procrastination, and academic achievement in adolescence. *Participatory Educational Research*, 9(2), 481–497. <http://dx.doi.org/10.17275/per.22.50.9.2>
- Ullrich, E. R. (2014). Parenting style as a moderator of child internalization of parental values (Master's thesis, Colorado State University). <https://search.proquest.com/openview/2a77a110d8a3f6f48e2923507a11c73c/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750>
- Viglas, M., & Perlman, M. (2018). Effects of a mindfulness-based program on young children's self-regulation, prosocial behavior and hyperactivity. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 27, 1150–1161. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10826-017-0971-6>
- Villavicencio, J. T., & Villavicencio, F. T. (2021). Self-compassion of Early Grade Students is Beneficial to their Academic Achievement. *Philippine Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 23(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13576500444000317>
- Voci, A., Veneziani, C. A., & Fuochi, G. (2019). Relating mindfulness, heartfulness, and psychological well-being: The role of self-compassion and gratitude. *Mindfulness*, 10(2), 339–351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-018-0978-0>
- Wang, J. (2022, January). Meta-analysis on the relationship between academic procrastination and parenting style. In 2021 International Conference on Social Development and Media Communication (SDMC 2021) (pp. 718–723). Atlantis Press. <https://doi.org/10.2991/assehr.k.220105.132>
- Widiyanti, A., & Najiyah, N. (2022). The Effect of a Permissive Parenting Style on the Main Character's Emotions and Behavior is Reflected in Greta Gerwig's *Lady Bird* (2017). *Metaphor*, 4(2), 23–39. <https://ojs.unsiq.ac.id/index.php/metaphor/article/view/3251>
- Willard, R., Possemato, K., Ramon, A., & Bergen-Cico, D. (2022). Self-compassion and self-judgment: Potential mediators of a mindfulness intervention on depression. *Journal of integrative and complementary medicine*, 28(7), 607–609. <https://doi.org/10.1089/jicm.2022.0511>
- Wolters, C. A., & Brady, A. C. (2021). College students' time management: A self-regulated learning perspective. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(4), 1319–1351. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09519-z>
- Xing, X., Liu, X., & Wang, M. (2019). Parental warmth and harsh discipline as mediators of the relations between family SES and Chinese preschoolers' inhibitory control. *Early Childhood Research Quarterly*, 48, 237–245. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecresq.2018.12.018>
- Yang, X., Liu, R. D., Ding, Y., Hong, W., & Jiang, S. (2021). The relations between academic procrastination and self-esteem in adolescents: A longitudinal study. *Current Psychology*, 1–15. <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1007/s12144-021-02075-x>
- Yarnell, L. M., Neff, K. D., Davidson, O. A., & Mullarkey, M. (2019). Gender differences in self-compassion: Examining the role of gender role orientation. *Personality and Individual Differences*, pp. 137, 122–125. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12671-018-1066-1>
- Yim, E. P. Y. (2022). Effects of Asian cultural values on parenting style and young children's perceived competence: A cross-sectional study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 905093. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.905093>
- Zarrin, S., Gracia, E., & Paixão, M. P. (2020). Prediction of academic procrastination by fear of failure and self-regulation. *Educational Sciences: Theory and Practice*, 20(3), 34–43. <http://dx.doi.org/10.12738/jestp.2020.3.003>
- Zhou, M., Lam, K. K. L., & Zhang, Y. (2022). Metacognition and academic procrastination: A meta-analytical examination. *Journal of Rational-Emotive & Cognitive-Behavior Therapy*, 40(2), 334–368. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10942-021-00415-1>
- Zonash, R., Arouj, K., & Jamala, B. (2021). Envious behavior among university students: Role of personality traits and self-compassion. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 9(1), 42–62. <https://www.academia.edu/download/84190762/34.pdf>

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